

Side effects: thrombosis-vaccinations-Sars-Cov2

The key point of this pandemic are the deaths from thrombosis, to lower the dead need to act on this element, regardless of the therapy for the infection, but the dilemma is that even vaccines, as the Covid-19 (Sars-cov2) produce infections, thrombosis is death, this is the objective truth, everyday, need to turn off the key point of the thrombosis, the virus doesn't trap. Doctors must not be politicians and politicians must not be doctors, doctors must save lives, block the dead and not increase the dead and politicians must promote economy, "print money" and not create debts to the population, hunger and despair, the set of all these events lead in one place, to the extinction of man.

Thrombosis: definition and generality

The term thrombosis collects all the events that accompany the formation of a thrombus inside a blood vessel, occluding it, disrupting circulation in the surrounding area.

Thrombosis: main causes

There are various possibilities of thrombotic processes. It all depends on the state of health of blood vessels, the density of blood, the functions of the mediators of aggregation and thrombosis. Venous and arterial thrombosis have or may have different causes. Arterial thrombosis arises from damage to the arterial wall, hyperlipidemia, smoking, hypertension, diabetes reduced physical activity, obesity. Venous thrombosis is mainly caused by blood stasis or abnormalities in the cascade of antithrombotic factors.

Thrombosis: diagnosis

The diagnosis of the disease thrombotic it is essential to collect the medical history and family history to identify, leading the doctors to understand the risk factors, the presence of thrombophilia, congenital or hereditary, through various examinations and laboratory testing that will lead the physician to the diagnosis and care suitable for investigating the possible factors congenital.

Congenital thrombophilia

Congenital thrombophilia is that situation present already from birth "hereditary thrombophilia" tending to promote and develop thrombosis. While acquired thrombophilia, it happens in the course of life.

Hereditary thrombophilia (coagulation factors)

General aspects: The inherited thrombophilia is a genetic predisposition that results in the formation of thrombi (blood clots), which promote the occurrence of deep venous thrombosis or arterial, or obstruction, partial or total, of the blood vessels, these prevent the normal flow of blood, in a few words it's like when the conduct of the sink in the kitchen, blocking, and does not descend to the water, so you need to act with the scale-removers to clean them. In the same way we proceed with thrombotic processes, which in the case of a failure and immediate remedy also lead to death. For example, thrombophilia in pregnancy, in cases of placental thrombosis, the obstruction of the blood vessels that bring nourishment to the fetus, can cause some complications, such as fetal growth retardation, placental detachment, etc.) until its spontaneous interruption. So thrombotic events are life-threatening events, and recent cases in the midst of a

pandemic confirm their dangerousness.

Recent studies have revealed the high accumulation of folates in the umbilical cord, due to non-conversion (UMFA), introductions of unsuitable folates, those not active, for those who have the genetic mutation, since they do not convert them for such abnormalities, leading all to an autistic increase for the fetus. So the integrations, the diets proposed by all the specialists, have not considered that 60% of the world's population does not use well the introductions we make starting from food, causing a chain damage for decades ignoring this gene that must convert substances to live, repair, promote chemical actions. Superficialities that comment themselves.

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Genetic aspects: the multiple genetic studies, involve day by day the predisposition of thrombotic events. Specifically those that encode the blood clotting factors such as Factor V and Factor II (Prothrombin), which are involved in the direct mode in the process of coagulation of the blood, involving the enzyme Metilentetraidrofolatoreduttasi (MTHFR) and its Genes, the same that led prosecutors to Italian to investigate and deepen the deaths after vaccination, of which were subsequently placed in the side effects. Most of the population is affected by such defects of coagulation, has followed the intersections double his feelings, and this is expressed in the heterozygous form, carrying a mutation in one of the two copies of the gene, transmissible to children, regardless of sex. In other subjects of the population, are altered both pairs of the gene are defined homozygous, but according to mathematical permutations, there are other possible intersections, because the two alleles and two forms, equal to six (6) possibility. DNA analysis allows to identify individuals carrying a specific mutation, both heterozygous and homozygous, C677T and A1298C, the former leads more to factors of blood circulation, leads more to factors at the expense of the nervous system, both alleles lead to the Union of these factors.

Factor V - is a protein that promotes heterozygous blood clotting process. In some subjects with the genetic mutation R506Q or G1691a or Arg506Gln, known as the Leiden variant, involves an increased pro-Coagulative activity of Factor V, resulting in an increased risk of developing venous thrombosis.

Factor II (prothrombin): the coagulation factor II or prothrombin, by the action of Factor V is transformed into thrombin which plays a fundamental role in the formation of the clot. DNA analysis for factor II identifies the g20210a mutation that leads to an increase in prothrombin levels in plasma with an increased risk of thrombosis.

Metilentetraidrofolatoreduttasi (MTHFR) is a protein that, unlike the factors II and V, is not directly involved in the process of blood clotting, but it acts in different ways, those metabolic including the transformation of homocysteine into the amino acid methionine, non-transformed becomes iperomocisteina, preparing thrombotic processes to the different stimuli that come from outside and from the inside. DNA analysis allows to identify the mutation C677T in the MTHFR gene which results in a 50% reduction in the activity of the protein which, unable to convert homocysteine to methionine; elevated plasma levels of homocysteine are considered a risk factor for the development of thrombosis. Recent studies indicate that homozygous subjects for the mutation have a 20% higher risk of venous thrombosis than normal homozygous ones.

In the other MTHFR gene, known as A1298C, which causes a reduction in enzyme activity of 30% if present individually, which does not appear to affect homocysteine in plasma, but rather affects the nervous system more. In addition, 60% in the heterozygous compounds C677T / A1298C that have, instead, high plasma values of homocysteine, predisposing them more to thrombosis. But the entanglements do not end here since in the mutation C677T heterozygosis combined with the Leiden variant (Factor V) or G20210A (factor II), it can further increase the risk of thrombotic events, already high due to the presence of the other mutation

The non-invasive modulators par excellence are the dietary orientation and the integration of natural phytotherapeutic active elements to make up for the lack of gene transformations from food.

The COVID-19 pandemic: a global health crisis

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